

PODIUM

Accelerating the implementation of CCAM technology

OBJECTIVES

PoDIUM will facilitate higher levels of automation by:

- assessing connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs;
- specifying the availability and performance of connectivity and cooperation;
- defining methods to ensure the quality and trust of external data;
- advancing key innovative technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure;
- defining a flexible platform architecture following a "multi-connectivity approach";
- examining feasibility and sustainability concepts in real traffic conditions;
- creating new business models and market services;
- promoting the project developments to standardisation bodies and policymakers;
- increasing road safety mainly for Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) and reducing automotive carbon footprint.

PoDIUM is a Horizon Europe Project that will identify and assess the connectivity and cooperation enablers to reach higher levels of automation and advance important Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) technologies, through a multi-connectivity approach and an interoperable and hybrid data management environment.

3 LIVING LABS, 5 USE CASES

- UC1:** Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm
- UC2:** Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance
- UC3:** Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel
- UC4:** Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)
- UC5:** Responsive PDI enabling Vehicles and Road Users to Self-Manage in Real-time for Mixed Traffic Optimisation on the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

EXPECTED IMPACT

- Provide increased road safety by providing real-time notifications about emergency cases;
- Improve the effectiveness of emergency services by sharing information about emergency incidents that require immediate access by public authorities;
- Improve traffic flow by providing real-time traffic data to the connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) and the rest of the vehicles;
- Lead to emissions reduction by shortening the time-to-destination for each driver;
- Minimize potential hazardous cases by increasing the Vulnerable Road User (VRU) detection rate.

«Advancing technologies both in physical and digital infrastructures (PDI) to accelerate the wider deployment of CCAM solutions and make higher levels of automation an everyday reality for all».

Dr Angelos Amditis (ICCS)
PoDIUM Coordinator

podium-project.eu

[PoDIUM_EU](https://twitter.com/PoDIUM_EU)

[PoDIUM Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/podium-project)

PROJECT INFO

Coordinated by ICCS (Institute of Communication & Computer Systems), the PoDIUM consortium comprises 24 partners from 8 European countries. The project runs from 1 October 2022 to 30 September 2025 and has a budget of €12.2M.

36 Months

24 Partners

3 Living Labs

CONSORTIUM

Co-funded by the European Union